

1 **Xist expression in triple negative breast cancer.**

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6 Xist is estrogen-repressible and evidence demonstrating that Xist is important for subtype selection in
7 breast cancer suggested that Xist might have a function in the development of triple negative breast
8 cancer. We describe here biologically significant expression of Xist in triple negative breast cancer. We
9 previously described roles for Xist non-coding RNA in treatment resistance and metastasis in TNBC. Xist
10 is expressed and likely important for development and survival of the triple negative breast cancer at
11 multiple steps: early in tumorigenesis following transformation during clonal selection, and later in the
12 cancer life cycle in disease progression and treatment resistance.

13 Citations

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17 differentiation and increases tumorigenicity through Mediator hyperactivation. Cell. 2022 Jun
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